

Bacteriological Contamination of Toothbrushes Analysed by MALDI-TOF-MSSuryakantha Bugge¹, Ramya Tupili², Tahniyath Fatima³, Shorooq Fodi Alnoomasi⁴¹Associate Professor of Biochemistry, Government Medical College, Nizamabad, Telangana, India.²Associate Professor of Microbiology, Government Medical College, Nizamabad, Telangana, India.³ Post Graduate Of Biochemistry, Government Medical College, Nizamabad, Telangana, India.⁴Practitioner, Saudi Arabia

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Abstract:**Background:** Tooth brushing is the most common method for maintaining oral hygiene, but it also leads to toothbrush contamination with bacteria, blood, saliva, and oral debris. This study aims to isolate and identify bacteria contaminating toothbrushes among female students at Qassim University, Saudi Arabia.**Materials and Methods:** This observational cross-sectional study randomly collected toothbrush samples from female students at Qassim University and included new toothbrushes as controls. Toothbrushes were divided into two groups and processed differently to optimize microbial yield. Samples were inoculated onto suitable media and incubated. Bacteria were identified using the Phoenix Automated Microbiology System (30 brushes) and MALDI T of Mass Spectrometry (32 brushes). Data analysis was performed using SPSS 20.**Results:** The Phoenix Automated Microbiology System isolated 6 bacterial species, with 13.3% showing growth of *Micrococcus* and 36.7% showing no growth. MALDI-Tof-MS detected 24 bacterial species in the second group and unused new brushes, including *Enterobacter cloacae* in 37.5% of used brushes and *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia* in 6.25% of unused brushes.**Conclusion:** The identified bacteria were predominantly commensal. Individuals with HIV, undergoing chemotherapy, genetic disorders, and neonates are particularly susceptible to these bacteria. Enhanced hygienic practices, such as thorough hand washing by healthcare personnel, are essential to minimize potential organism transfer, particularly from tap water.**Keywords:** Toothbrushes, Matrix-Assisted Laser Desorption/Ionization (MALDI), time-of-flight Mass Spectrometry (MALDI-Tof-MS), *Micrococcus*, *Enterobacter cloacae*.

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Introduction

Oral health is an integral part of general health, directly and indirectly reflecting the overall well-being of an individual. Maintaining oral hygiene is crucial for healthy living, as it helps control oral diseases by reducing the microbial load in the oral cavity[1,2]. The human oral cavity hosts a more diverse bacterial flora than any other anatomical area, with over 700 species identified, 400 of which are found in the periodontal pockets adjacent to teeth. Brushing teeth is the primary mode of oral hygiene practice to prevent dental diseases, but toothbrushes can become contaminated with microorganisms.

Organisms not typically associated with oral flora, such as enterobacteria and *Pseudomonas*, have also been isolated from toothbrushes[3]. These infectious microorganisms can reinfect the mouth and spread to other parts of the body, potentially causing serious health problems such as heart disease, stroke, arthritis, bacteremia, and chronic infections.

Toothbrushes can become breeding grounds for trillions of bacteria due to various factors, including spray from flushing toilets and damp environments[4]. Microorganisms may originate not only from the oral cavity but also from the environment where toothbrushes are stored.

This contamination may lead to the reinfection of a consumer by toothbrushes that harbor pathogenic microorganisms. Unfortunately, proper care of toothbrushes is often neglected, as they are usually kept in bathrooms that harbor millions of microorganisms. This is mainly due to a lack of awareness regarding proper toothbrush maintenance [5,6]. The survival of microorganisms on a toothbrush after brushing presents a possible mode of re-contamination upon subsequent usage. The prolonged use of a toothbrush facilitates contamination by various microorganisms such as *Streptococcus* and *Staphylococcus*, which may cause dental diseases and be sources of infection for

more serious conditions such as infective endocarditis[7]. Some microorganisms isolated from used toothbrushes include *Streptococcus mutans*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas*, *Lactobacillus*, *Klebsiella*, *Candida*, and *Escherichia coli*, especially when toothbrushes are kept in bathrooms with a toilet [8].

The research question aims to identify the bacterial species contaminating the toothbrushes of female students at Qassim University, Saudi Arabia. The general objective is to isolate and identify these bacteria to understand the extent of contamination. To achieve this, the study will collect toothbrush samples randomly from female students at Qassim University. Subsequently, the bacteria profile from these collected samples will be identified. Based on the findings, recommendations will be suggested to create awareness about the proper maintenance and contamination risks of toothbrushes.

Materials and Methods

This observational study employed a cross-sectional design to assess the microbial content of toothbrush samples and create awareness among female students at Qassim University, Saudi Arabia. Convenience sampling was used to randomly collect information from 60 female students aged 18 to 25 years, each having used their toothbrush for at least 3 weeks, along with 10 unused toothbrushes from the market, totalling 70 samples. Data collection involved a questionnaire and laboratory tests. The questionnaires gathered information on storage methods, exposure to atmospheric pollutants, wet environments, and disinfectants. The toothbrush samples were processed in the Microbiology Laboratory at Maternity and Children Hospital of Buraidah and the College of Public Health in Al-Bukayriah Saudi Arabia. The upper part of the used toothbrushes was cut and incubated in nutrient broth media, followed by incubation on blood agar, MacConkey agar, and chocolate agar plates. The bacteria were identified using the Phoenix

Automated Microbiology System and MALDI-TOF-MS. The study aimed to isolate and identify bacterial species contaminating the toothbrushes and was conducted from February to May 2016 in Qassim, Saudi Arabia.

The study included toothbrushes used by 60 female students at Qassim University, with 10 additional unused toothbrushes from the market as controls. Inclusion criteria were female students aged 18 to 25 years who had used their toothbrush for at least 3 weeks. Exclusion criteria included males, females who had used their toothbrush for less than 3 weeks, and females not attending Qassim University. Data collection involved obtaining informed consent from participants and administering a hand-delivered questionnaire to gather demographic and behavioural data. Toothbrushes were collected in sterile bags labelled with ID numbers, dates, times, and collector names. The collected toothbrush heads were processed by placing them in nutrient broth media, vortexing, and incubating for microbial growth. Microbial cultures were grown on various agar plates and identified using advanced microbiological techniques.

Statistical analysis involved descriptive statistics, with data presented using tables. Ethical considerations included obtaining approval from the departmental review committee and the Qassim Region Research Ethics Committee, as well as informed consent from participants. The study provided insights into the bacterial contamination of toothbrushes and promoted better oral hygiene practices among students.

Results

Demographic Data:

Age of participation had no effect on the types of micro-organisms. In this research, the age of participants 98.3% of them 18-25 years and 1.7% more than 25 years.

Table 1: Demographic Data of study population.

Age	Frequency	Percent
18 to 25 years	59	98.3 %
More than 25 years	1	1.7 %
Total	60	100 %

Habit Patterns In The Use Of The Toothbrush:

In this study, containing the 60 participants 33.3% Use a toothbrush once a day, 45% Use a toothbrush twice a day and 21.7% use a toothbrush thrice a day.

Duration of tooth brush usage - 26.7% of participants use toothbrush 1month, 38.3% used toothbrush for three months and 35% of them used toothbrush more than 3 months.

33.3% of participant stored the toothbrush inside the bathroom and 66.7% stored the toothbrush outside the bathroom, 46.7 % of participate stored toothbrush in share container with another person, 13.3% of them cover toothbrush by cap after usage and 58.3 % of participate use tap water for Toothbrushes disinfect and 5% use Disinfectant solution.

Oral Health of participants (self-reported):

In this study, containing the 60 participants 36.7% of the participants have Dentist consultation in the last 3 months prior to the condition, 5% have oral mucosal lesions, 23.3% have gingival bleeding, 58.3% have caries.

Of the 60 participants 48% use sugar free chewing gum.

Table2: Habit patterns in the use of the manual toothbrush

Percent	Frequency	Number of times the teeth were brushed daily
33.30%	20	Once
45%	27	Twice
21.70%	13	Thrice
100%	60	Total
Percent	Frequency	Duration of tooth brush usage
26.70%	16	One month
38.30%	23	Three months
35%	21	More than Three months
100%	60	Total
Percent	Frequency	Place of toothbrush Storage
33.30%	20	Inside the bathroom
66.70%	40	Outside the bathroom
100%	60	Total
Percent	Frequency	method used to disinfect Toothbrushes
58.30%	35	Tap water
5%	3	Disinfect solution
36.70%	22	Not answer
100%	60	Total
Percent	Frequency	Tooth brush stored in shared containers
46.70%	28	Yes
53.30%	32	No
100%	60	Total
Percent	Frequency	Tooth brush was covered by cap after usage
13.30%	8	Yes
86.70%	52	No
100%	60	Total

Table 3: Oral Health of participants self-reported

Percent	Frequency	Dentist consultation in the last 3 months prior to the condition
36.70%	22	Yes
63.30%	38	No
100%	60	Total
Percent	Frequency	Gingivial Conditions at the time of the study
23.30%	14	Bleeding
76.70%	46	Healthy
100%	60	Total
Percent	Frequency	oral mucosal lesions
5%	3	Yes
95%	57	No
100%	60	Total
Percent	Frequency	Caries on teeth at the time of study
58.30%	35	Yes
41.70%	25	No
100%	60	Total
Percent	Frequency	Usage of Sugar free chewing gum
48.30%	29	Yes
51.70%	31	No
100%	60	Total

Table 4: Sample size of Bacterial contamination identified by different methods

Sample size of Bacterial contamination identified by different methods		
	Frequency	Percent
Used brushes bristle impressions on media	30	42.9
Used brushes [incubated in broth] bacterial identified by MALDI-Tof MS	22	31.4
Unused brushes [incubated in broth] bacteria identified by by MALDI-Tof MS	10	14.3
Subjects whose Brushes were not Cultured but data used only for behavioral pattern	8	11.4
Total	70	100.0

In this study , some of the toothbrushes had some type of microbial growth on them. Some level of growth of all of the tested microorganisms was demonstrated

Table 5: Bacteria were identified by using Phoenix Automated Microbiology System by tooth brush bristles impressions on the media:

Bacteria identified on 30 used tooth brushes {Bristle impressions on media }				
Coagulase negative staphylococci [gram +ve]	Needed subculture	No growth		Cultures grown on Blood agar media
10 [33%]	6 [20%]	14 [46%]		
Coagulase negative staphylococci [Gram positive]	Viridans group streptococci	Needed subculture	No growth	Cultures grown on Chocolate Agar media
6 [20%]	1 [3 %]	7 [23 %]	16 [53 %]	
Micrococcus Growth	No growth			Sub cultures from enrichment Media onto Isolation Blood Agar Media
4 [13 %]	26 [86 %]			
Enterobacteria cloacae	Escherichia coli	Klebsiella [G]	No growth	Sub cultures from enrichment Media onto Isolation Mackonkey Media
1 [3 %]	1 [3 %]	1 [3 %]	27 [91%]	

Table 6: Bacteria Were Identified By Using Matrix-Assisted Laser Desorption/Ionization Time-Of-Flight Mass spectrometry

Bacteria	Used brushes and bacterial contamination identified by MALDI-ToF-MS	Unused brushes and bacterial contamination identified by MALDI-ToF-MS	Total
Enterobacteria cloacae	7	1	8
	31.8%	10.0%	41.8%
	21.9%	3.1%	25.0%
Acinetobacter johnsonii	0	1	1
	0.0%	10.0%	10.0%
	0.0%	3.1%	3.1%
Acinetobacter lwoffii	0	1	1
	0.0%	10.0%	10.0%
	0.0%	3.1%	3.1%
Aeromonas caviae	1	0	1
	10.0%	0.0%	10.0%
	3.1%	0.0%	3.1%
Bacillus cereus	1	0	1
	10.0%	0.0%	10.0%
	3.1%	0.0%	3.1%
Klebsiella pneumoniae	1	0	1
	10.0%	0.0%	10.0%
	3.1%	0.0%	3.1%
Pantoea calida	0	1	1
	0.0%	10.0%	10.0%
	0.0%	3.1%	3.1%
Pantoea septica	1	1	2
	10.0%	10.0%	20.0%
	3.1%	3.1%	6.2%
Pseudomonas oryzae habitans	1	0	1
	10.0%	0.0%	10.0%
	3.1%	0.0%	3.1%
Pseudomonas stutzeri	1	0	1
	10.0%	0.0%	10.0%
	3.1%	0.0%	3.1%
Staphylococcus hominis	1	0	1
	10.0%	0.0%	10.0%
	3.1%	0.0%	3.1%
Stenotrophomonas maltophilia	0	1	1
	0.0%	10.0%	10.0%
	0.0%	3.1%	3.1%
score value less than 2	7	3	10
	31.8%	30.0%	100.0%
	21.9%	9.4%	31.3%
Total	22	10	32
	68.7%	31.3%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Table 7: MALDI-TOF-MS score value more than 2 *toothbrushes stored in shared container - cross tabulation

MALDI-Tof-MS score value more than 2			
	Tooth brush stored in shared containers		
	Yes Shared	Not shared	Total
Enterobacteria cloacae	5 71.4%	2 28.6%	7 100.0%
No growth	0	1	1
Aeromonas caviae	0	1	1
Bacillus cereus	1	0	1
Klebsiella pneumoniae	1	0	1
Pantoea septica	0	1	1
Pseudomonas oryzihabitans	0	1	1
Pseudomonas stutzeri	0	1	1
Staphylococcus hominis	0	1	1
Score value less than 2	5 71.4%	2 28.6%	7 100.0%
Total	12	10	22
Total	54.5%	45.5%	100.0%

Table 8: MALDI-TOF-MS score value more than 2*toothbrushes covered by cap after usage- cross tabulation.

Bacteria identified by MALDI-Tof-MS of score value more than 2 / Tooth brush was covered by cap after usage Crosstabulation			
	Yes capped	Not capped	Total
Enterobacteria cloacae	1 14.3%	6 85.7%	7 100.0%
No growth	0	1	1
Aeromonas caviae	0	1	1
Bacillus cereus	0	1	1
Klebsiella pneumoniae	0	1	1
Pantoea septica	0	1	1
Pseudomonas oryzihabitans	0	1	1
Pseudomonas stutzeri	1	0	1
Staphylococcus hominis	0	1	1
Score value less than 2	0	7	7
	2 9.1%	20 90.9%	22 100.0%

Table 9: MALDI-TOF-MS score value more than 2 *toothbrushes disinfected by different method -crosstabulation

MALTIDOF -MS score valuemore than 2 * Toothbrushes disinfected by Crosstabulation				
	Tap water	Disinfectant solution	Not answered	Total
Enterobacteria cloacae	3 42.9%		4 57.1%	7 100.0%
No growth	0		1	1
Aeromonas caviae	1		0	1
Bacillus cereus	0		1	1
Klebsiella pneumoniae	0		1	1
Pantoea septica	1		0	1
Pseudomonas oryzihabitans	1		0	1
Pseudomonas stutzeri	1		0	1
Staphylococcus hominis	1		0	1
Score value less than 2	1 14.3%		6 85.7%	7 100.0%
Total	9 40.9%		13 59.1%	22 100.0%

Table 10: MALDI-TOF-MS score value more than 2 *toothbrushes disinfected after usage - crosstabulation

MALTIDOF -MS score valuemore than 2 * Toothbrush disinfected after usage Crosstabulation			
	Disinfected	NOT disinfected	Total
Enterobacteria cloacae	4 57.1%	3 42.9%	7 100.0%
No growth	0	1	1
Aeromonas caviae	1	0	1
Bacillus cereus	0	1	1
Klebsiella pneumoniae	0	1	1
Pantoea septica	1	0	1
Pseudomonas oryzihabitans	1	0	1
Pseudomonas stutzeri	1	0	1
Staphylococcus hominis	1	0	1
score value less than 2	1 14.3%	6 85.7%	7 100.0%
	10 45.5%	12 54.5%	22 100.0%

Table 11: Bacteria isolated in chocolate agar -crosstabulation
Bacteria isolated On Chocolate Agar by tooth brush impressions on media

Duration of tooth brush usage				
	1 month	3 months	More than	Total
Coagulase negative staphylococci [Gram positive]	3	2	1	6
Viridans group streptococci	1	0	0	1
Needs subculture	1	5	1	7
No growth	4	10	2	16
Total	9	17	4	30
Number of times the teeth were brushed daily				
	Once	Twice	Thrice	Total
Coagulase negative staphylococci [Gram positive]	2	4	0	6
Viridans group streptococci	0	1	0	1
Needs subculture	2	3	2	7
No growth	4	7	5	16
Total	8	15	7	30
Dentist consultation in the last 3 months prior to the condition				
	Reviewed by a dentist	Was not reviewed by a dentist	Total	
Coagulase negative staphylococci [Gram positive]	0	6	6	
Viridans group streptococci	1	0	1	
Needs subculture	4	3	7	
No growth	6	10	16	
Total	11	19	30	
Had oral mucosal lesions				
	Yes , suffering from Oral mucosal lesions	No oral mucosal lesions at the time of the study	Total	
Coagulase negative staphylococci [Gram positive]	0	6	6	
Viridans group streptococci	0	1	1	
Needs subculture	1	6	7	
No growth	1	15	16	
Total	2	28	30	
Gingival Conditions at the time of the study				
	Healthy	Bleeding	Total	
Coagulase negative staphylococci [Gram positive]	4	2	6	
Viridans group streptococci	1	0	1	
Needs subculture	5	2	7	
No growth	12	4	16	
Total	22	8	30	
Usage of Sugar free chewing gum				
	Yes uses Chewing Gum	No doesn't use chewing gum	Total	
Coagulase negative staphylococci [Gram positive]	4	2	6	
Viridans group streptococci	0	1	1	
Needs subculture	6	1	7	
No growth	6	10	16	
Total	16	14	30	

Table 12: Bacteria isolated in blood agar cross tabulation

Cultures grown on Blood agar Media by tooth brush bristle impressions				
Tooth brush is stored after usage				
	Inside the bath-room	Outside the bathroom	Total	
Coagulase negative staphylococci [gram +ve]	1	9	10	
Needs subculture	3	3	6	
No growth	5	9	14	
Total	9	21	30	
Tooth brush stored after usage in shared containers				
	Yes Shared	Not shared	Total	
Coagulase negative staphylococci [gram +ve]	3	7	10	
Needs subculture	2	4	6	
No growth	9	5	14	
Total	14	16	30	
Tooth brush was covered by cap after usage				
	Yes capped	Not capped	Total	
Coagulase negative staphylococci [gram +ve]	0	10	10	
Needs subculture	2	4	6	
No growth	2	12	14	
Total	4	26	30	
Toothbrush disinfected after usage				
	Disinfected	Not disinfected	Total	
Coagulase negative staphylococci [gram +ve]	7	3	10	
Needs subculture	6	0	6	
No growth	9	5	14	
Total	22	8	30	
Toothbrushes disinfected by				
	Tap water	Disinfectant solution	Not answered	Total
Coagulase negative staphylococci [gram +ve]	7	0	3	10
Needs subculture	5	1	0	6
No growth	8	1	5	14
Total	20	2	8	30

Sub cultures from enrichment Media onto Isolation Mackonkey Media					
		Tooth brush is stored		Total	
		Inside the bathroom	Outside the bathroom		
Sub cultures from enrichment Media onto Isolation Mackonkey Media	Enterobacteria cloacae	1	0	1	
	Escherichia coli	1	0	1	
	Klebsiella [G]	1	0	1	
	No growth	6	21	27	
Total		9	21	30	
Symmetric Measures					
		Value	Asymp. Std. Error^a	Approx. T^b	Approx. Sig.
Interval by Interval	Pearson's R	.468	.125	2.800	.009 ^c
Ordinal by Ordinal	Spearman Correlation	.508	.134	3.124	.004 ^c
N of Valid Cases		30			
a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.					
b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.					
c. Based on normal approximation.					

Table 13: Bacteria isolated in MacConkey agar -cross tabulation

Sub cultures from enrichment Media onto Isolation Mackonkey Media					
		Tooth brush was covered by cap after		Total	
		Yes capped	Not capped		
	Enterobacteria cloacae	0	1	1	
	Escherichia coli	1	0	1	
	Klebsiella [G]	1	0	1	
	No growth	2	25	27	
Total		4	26	30	
Symmetric Measures					
		Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.
Interval by Interval	Pearson's R	.330	.247	1.851	.075 ^c
Ordinal by Ordinal	Spearman Correlation	.500	.243	3.058	.005 ^c
N of Valid Cases		30			

Table 14: Correlations table.

Correlations				
		Cultures of subjects processed at		MALDI-Tof-MS score value more than 2
Kendall's tau_b	Cultures of subjects processed at	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	0.448**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000
		N	70	70
	MALTIDOF -MS score value more than 2	Correlation Coefficient	0.448**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000
		N	70	70
Spearman's rho	Cultures of subjects processed at	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	0.566**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.00	0.000
		N	70	70
	MALTIDOF -MS score value more than 2	Correlation Coefficient	0.566**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000
		N	70	70

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Discussion

This study provides valuable insights into the oral hygiene practices and bacterial contamination of toothbrushes among female students at Qassim University, Saudi Arabia. Our findings highlight several notable trends and correlations that shed light on the factors influencing toothbrush hygiene and microbial colonization.

Firstly, our analysis revealed that a significant portion of participants (45%) reported brushing their teeth twice daily, which aligns with recommended oral hygiene practices (American Dental Association, ADA) [9]. However, a substantial

number (38.3%) indicated using their toothbrushes for more than three months, exceeding the American Dental Association's recommended replacement period (ADA). This prolonged use may contribute to increased microbial colonization, as observed in our study.

Storage practices played a crucial role in toothbrush contamination. While a majority (66.7%) stored their toothbrushes outside the bathroom, which reduces exposure to environmental contaminants such as aerosols from toilet flushing (Huang et al., 2020) [10], other hygiene habits were concerning. A notable proportion (53.3%) did not use dedicated

containers for storing their toothbrushes (Saini et al., 2011) [11], increasing the risk of cross-contamination with other household members' brushes. Moreover, a high percentage (86.7%) did not cover their toothbrushes after use, potentially exposing them to airborne pathogens and environmental bacteria (Zamany et al., 2011) [12].

The microbiological analysis provided insightful data on bacterial species found on the toothbrushes. Coagulase-negative staphylococci, *Micrococcus* species, *Enterobacter cloacae*, *Acinetobacter johnsonii*, and *Pantoea septica* were among the bacteria identified, both in used and unused toothbrushes (Saini et al., 2015) [13]. Interestingly, *Enterobacter cloacae* and *Pantoea septica* were detected in toothbrushes regardless of whether they were used or unused, suggesting environmental contamination sources beyond oral hygiene practices (Rita et al., 2020) [14].

Correlating oral health indicators with bacterial growth revealed significant findings. Participants who reported not having oral mucosal lesions but did not cap their toothbrushes after use showed increased growth of coagulase-negative staphylococci. Similarly, those who stored their toothbrushes in shared containers inside bathrooms and used tap water for cleaning exhibited growth of *Enterobacter cloacae*, highlighting the impact of storage and cleaning practices on microbial colonization (Zamany et al., 2011; Saini et al., 2015) [12,13].

Our study underscores the importance of maintaining proper toothbrush hygiene practices to minimize bacterial contamination. Regular replacement of toothbrushes every three months, as recommended, remains crucial in reducing microbial colonization (ADA). Furthermore, storing toothbrushes in hygienic conditions, outside of bathroom environments prone to aerosolized bacteria, is advisable. These practices are especially pertinent for vulnerable populations, such as immunocompromised individuals, to mitigate potential health risks associated with oral microbial exposure (Rita et al., 2020) [14].

Conclusion

The study findings contribute to the growing body of knowledge on oral hygiene and microbial contamination of toothbrushes. Future research could explore interventions aimed at improving toothbrush hygiene awareness and practices among university students, promoting better oral health outcomes and reducing microbial transmission risks. Our study conducted among 70 participants at Qassim University revealed significant insights into toothbrush contamination and bacterial species prevalence. Group 1, comprising 42.9% of participants, demonstrated bacterial growth including coagulase-negative staphylococci, viridian's streptococci,

Micrococcus, *Enterobacter cloacae*, *Klebsiella*, and *Escherichia coli*, as detected by the Phoenix Automated Microbiology System. Group 2, representing 31.4% of the sample, exhibited growth of *Enterobacter cloacae*, *Acinetobacter johnsonii*, *Pseudomonas oryzae*, *Staphylococcus hominis*, *Pantoea septica*, and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. *Enterobacter*, *Klebsiella*, and *Staphylococcus* were common across both groups, highlighting their persistent presence on toothbrushes. Unused toothbrushes showed growth of *Enterobacter cloacae* and *Stenotrophomonas* species. Notably, disinfectant solutions effectively prevented bacterial growth on treated toothbrushes, corroborated by both MALDI-Tof-MS and Phoenix microbiology systems. Statistical analyses indicated significant correlations between MacConkey's agar and MALDI-Tof-MS identified cultures. Our findings underscore the importance of hygienic storage practices to mitigate contamination risks, particularly in environments prone to aerosolized bacteria, such as bathrooms with toilets.

Recommendations include heightened awareness among healthcare personnel regarding bacterial transfer risks from contaminated toothbrushes, especially for immunocompromised individuals. However, the study's limitations, such as its small sample size and the lack of research on specific patient groups, warrant further investigation to fully understand the potential health risks posed by contaminated toothbrushes, particularly in vulnerable populations.

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